

Learning Through Listening: An Autoethnographic Approach

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Abstract. From the point-of-audition, we ask: what interferes with listening? Listening in/to the world from my standpoint, I bring in personal experience and knowledge. Autoethnographic research allows us to connect with the bigger picture and engage with our surroundings. Echoing Barad, I argue that researchers are part of the physical world rather than observers looking at the world (2007, 376). Thus, knowing constitutes a “physical practice of engagement” (Barad, 2007, 342). By including this new materialist perspective, I consider non-human forms of agency in autoethnographic research, thereby shifting the focus on relational networks rather than focusing solely on human action.

With an emphasis on the act of listening, I propose the adoption of the “listener-as-student” stance (McRae, 2012). Listening critically in/to the world, into ourselves and towards others, we gain knowledge. In terms of artistic research, it makes sense to investigate the self in order to reveal an internal individual view of the creative process. Self-reflection enables awareness of misconceptions, expectations, and prejudices that interfere with listening and learning. We are able to form new understandings by balancing information acquired from within and without.

Following research previously conducted as part of the project *On the Fragility of Sounds* hosted at the University of Music and Performing Arts Graz, I will posit an example of an autoethnographic approach towards listening: I will present how the composer Pia Palme engages with listening and autoethnography in her artistic research process.

Intro

This paper is an experiment in thinking about artistic research with a new materialist perspective. I ask: “How might a new materialist approach both affect (and become affected by) autoethnographic research of sound and listening?” I look at autoethnographic research as a method of engaged knowledge production and consider the significance of listening practices within this process. By adopting a new materialist approach derived from Gender Studies, concepts of diffraction/interferences and their potential in research are evaluated. To address the research question, I will refer to works and artistic concepts by the composer, performer, and theorist Pia Palme. For full disclosure, it is necessary to explain how I came to write with/about her and her practice. Since 2019 we have both been working on the artistic research project *On the Fragility of Sounds*, funded by the Austrian science fund FWF (Project AR 537). This influences my research in multiple ways. On the one hand, it allows me to join music practices, experience working processes, and talk to the composer-performer and her collaborators. It enables me to have a deeper look into this music practice and art form. On the other hand, it challenges my objectivity in my research activities, because within the project, Pia Palme is not only my colleague, but also my superior. It is therefore of great importance for me to stay critically aware of our intra-active research activities, our entanglement, and our interferences.

Turning to new materialism

The dominant approach to gender studies has long been informed by postmodern and post-structuralist theories. In this approach, researchers have focused mainly on language/discourses and representations, thereby disregarding materiality. Or as Karan Barad put it: “Language matters. Discourse matters. Culture matters. There is an important sense in which the only thing that does not seem to matter anymore is matter” (Barad, 2003, p. 801). By adopting a new materialist approach, feminist researchers consider matter as an active factor in the becoming of the world. Further, the central position of the human as opposed to nature is contested, which allows the exploration of non-human factors and the relationship between humans and non-humans.

Autoethnography as an artistic research method

Autoethnographic research means to “I-witness” (Spry, 2001) the world, by means of connecting, describing, and analyzing personal experiences in relation to a given cultural and socio-economic context. Autoethnographic research is not an approach to explore the self, but to understand socio-cultural phenomena through the lens of the researcher (Heewon, 2013, p. 108). Autoethnographic insights give others the possibility of relating to the stories and making sense of their own experiences: “As autoethnographers, we try to contribute to existing research and theory by using personal experience to describe, understand, and challenge cultural practices and beliefs” (Adams, Holmes Jones & Ellis, 2015, p. 38).

Autoethnography, as an artistic research method, is not only concerned with conventional knowledge production but “with the emotional, sensory, and embodied experience of social life” (Adams & Holman Jones, 2018, p. 146). Generated knowledge is not only written down and readable, but also experienced sensually: “Autoethnographic texts seek to invoke the corporeal, sensuous, and political nature of experience rather than collapse text into embodiment or politics into language play” (Holman Jones, 2005, p. 767). Thus, autoethnographies can be written, visual, and/or aural manifestations of self-reflexive knowledge. Whereas traditional research presents explicit outcomes, autoethnographic texts and performances do not necessarily offer conclusive findings (Holman Jones, 2005, p. 772). More and more artists are exploring self-reflexive practices such as autoethnography. This makes sense; after all, the purpose of artistic research is not to produce formal knowledge, but to “provide a specific articulation of the pre-reflective, nonconceptual content of art” (Borgdorff, 2012, p. 143).

Adapting a new materialist approach, autoethnography shifts from a reflexive to a diffractive practice, from mirroring to patterns of differences (Barad, 2007, 29). It challenges the idea of the authentic self – a notion at the very heart of autoethnography. Here the human is not conceptualized as a stable entity (‘subject’), looking at the world (‘object’), but as relational, partial, and entangled, which is also true for every other mode of being (Mellander & Wiszmeg, 2016, p. 102). This means, researchers are *part of* the physical world rather than

observers looking *at the world* (Barad, 2007, p. 376). Thus, knowing constitutes a “physical practice of engagement” (Barad, 2007, p. 342). By shifting the focus to relational networks and the co-production of knowledge by humans/material (Vu, 2018, p. 76-77), the experience of the autoethnographer is no longer the stable source of knowledge (Jackson & Mazzei, 2008, p. 304). Adopting a diffractive methodology means to acknowledge one’s own interference and entanglement with the world. Thinking with Barad’s concept of “diffraction,” used by the author interchangeably with “interferences,” autoethnographic research “investigates the material-discursive boundary-making practices that produce [...] differences out of, and in terms of, a changing relationality” (Barad, 2007, p. 93).

Autoethnography itself can be understood as a material-discursive knowledge practice effecting *agential cuts*, hence producing differences and performing new realities. Through this practice, meaning is generated (Barad, 2007, p. 148; Jespersen et al., 2012, p. 8). A diffractive approach, according to Barad, does not describe generated differences but “is a commitment to understanding which differences matter, how they matter, and for whom” (Barad, 2007, p. 90). For autoethnography, this means on the one hand, to question one’s own knowledge and on the other hand to confront one’s own privilege and authority in listening, telling, writing, and performing (Vu, 2018, p. 80).

Learning through listening

Listening is one way for humans and *more-than-humans*¹ to explore the world. Here, the researcher’s senses and body are part of knowledge production. As autoethnographic researchers advocate for a heightened “body-reflexivity” (Valtonen & Haanpää, 2018; Spry, 2001), listening to oneself, but also listening to others and non-humans, is considered an appropriate methodological tool in autoethnographic research.

Although hearing is a physical bodily process, it is not a neutral one. It is rather an active and creative practice (Clarke, 2005; Carlyle, 2013, p. 16) that is physically, historically, socially, locally, and culturally influenced (Sterne, 2012, p. 4; McRae, 2015, p. 336). We *know-with* and *know-through* the audible, as Steven Feld phrased it (Feld, 2015, p. 12). Listening is also considered political. Composer Pauline Oliveros, for example, famously framed her listening practice as political and inclusive (2005, p. 15); Pia Palme explores the concept of a “feminist listening” practice (Palme, 2017, p. 46). And Eidsheim (2019, p. 24) explains: “Because listening is never neutral, but rather always actively produces meaning, it is a political act. Through listening, we name and define. We get to say, ‘This is the voice of a black man.’ We get to say, ‘That singer doesn’t sound sincere.’ And we get to say, ‘This singer doesn’t sound like herself.’”

1. “More-than-human” is a term widely used in the Posthumanities. Although there is no clear definition of the term, it challenges the nature-culture divide and positions the human as “entangled in co-constitutive relationships with nature and the environment, with science and technology, with vulnerable embodiments of both human and nonhuman kinds” (Åsberg & Braidotti, 2018, p. 10). Here, the term is used to emphasize the agency of non-human actors, like non-human animals.

In autoethnographic research, it makes sense to address one's listening practice in more detail in order to learn from it. Through our listening practice we intra-act with our surroundings, not only with human voices but also with surfaces, locations, soundwaves, and other materiality. By moving we change wave-patterns, we interfere with sound, we affect our listening experience. Listening, thinking again with new materialism, is a practice that contributes to the becoming of the world. Here I want to introduce McRae's concept of *performative listening* (2012, 2015) as a method of inquiry. He defines listening as embodied, critical, reflexive, and engaged learning practice (McRae, 2015, p. 31). By "listening-as-student" one is open and willing to learn and take responsibility for one's listening practice. I want to interfere with his useful concept, by replacing "reflexive" with "diffractive."

Through listening, one (re)produces social constructs like gender, race, and class. A diffractive practice is able to disrupt the act of listening by posing questions like: Which differences are generated through my listening? Where do I direct my attention? Where not? How do I make sense of the surrounding sound waves? How can I intra-act and disrupt my preconceptions and listening practice? How is meaning actively produced from the intra-action of listeners and the world?

The composer and the island

Composer Pia Palme explores the idea of a feminist practice in composition. Her interest lies in political "composing-as-listening," rather than composing feminist works (Palme, 2017, p. 14). In her writing she develops a concept of "the feminist ear" that denotes "listening from a feminist position" (Palme, 2017, p. 22). She describes her compositional practice as "grounded in feminism, meaning that feminism underpins how and what kind of decisions are made during the compositional process and around it" (Palme, 2017, p. 14). Her practice is informed by feminist theory, sound art, cognitive science, and experimental music discourses on listening. She herself suggests interpreting her listening practice as "diffractive":

My mode of listening into phenomena is subversive and creative; it defines a feminist practice. Activating the feminist ear, I listen to contextual sonorities: sound is located within its aural environment. Listening to the background noises of human interaction brings them to the foreground of my perception and awareness. In this way, feminist listening spans the external and internal spatial expanses, integrating human and non-human sonorities (Palme, 2017, p. 25).

Pia Palme's engagement with (autoethnographic) writing constitutes another integral part of her creative work. These listening and writing practices allow her to critically reflect misconceptions, expectations, and prejudices that interfere with listening and learning. One is able to form new understandings by balancing information acquired from within and without. Through "composing-as-listening," Pia Palme's sonic autoethnographies materialize

phenomena in intra-action with humans and non-humans. Here, the self is destabilized. As noted earlier, a new materialist autoethnography challenges the notion of the subject position. We come to understand the world through the self. We learn, feel, and observe through the self, the “witnessing I,” always situated in time and place. But identities are not fixed entities; they are fragile, ever-changing, moving, shifting, relational – and so is the expression and performance of subjectivity in Pia Palme’s work. Her experimental music theater pieces do not stage characters with names, but fragmented identities. Some of her most recent works *Dusk Songs* (2019), *Mattetoline* (2019), and *Isolation Island* (2020)² illustrate her engagement with musical autoethnography. Through these pieces she explores and performs her observations and experiences on the Finnish island Öro. They allow the audience to listen to the composer’s (listening) experience with/to the island. The island, as a location, is historically, culturally, and socially structured and serves as a powerful agent in her performance of listening. She does not merely listen to the island, but intra-acts with the island as listener. The entanglement of the composer’s activities and the island is obvious when Pia Palme performs with the deserted carpet hanger at the end of *Mattetoline*. Pia Palme’s moving on the island contributed to the becoming of the island’s sound. Her positionality and physicality are inextricably entangled with the becoming of these phenomena. Listening to/with the island “is an act that produces the location as meaningful” (McRae, 2012, p. 340). During the development of *Mattetoline* I was able to observe how the composer listened to her collaborators. Their voices and sounds interfered and influenced the becoming of the piece. In doing so, this practice challenges the idea of composing as creative practice of a single (male) genius.

Illustration 1. Pia Palme, performing with a carpet hanger on the Finnish island Öro, © Pia Palme

2 Listen to Pia Palme’s music on her website <https://piapalme.at/works/> (accessed on 02.03.2022).

In her experimental music theatre *Mattetoline* she arranges her “noise of mind” as compositional material (Palme, 2017). By exploring autoethnography, these pieces offer a glimpse into the “inner voices” of the composer-performer; we can listen to the composer’s performative listening. The self changes as do the surroundings. It is an observation of time, location, people, and things. The self is the moment, fleeting being, as well as becoming anew in every single moment. This sonic autoethnography is a performance of the human condition, problems, and thoughts of a woman composer, in this time and place, trapped on an island, explored by herself and expressed with/through the voices of herself and the soprano Annette Schön Müller.

The two voices, performed by the composer and the singer, talk from the perspective of a person being on a lonely island. Both voices seem to originate from the same mind, like “inner voices” that are never consistent and singular, but often dialogic, contradicting, and challenging. In these pieces, we do not hear only a singer and a vocal performer, but a polyphony of voices. This is realized through different timbres, sound effects, and vocal styles: extended vocal techniques, vocal fry, non-pitched sounds, the use of breath, specific articulations, and experiments with vowels. At one specific moment, when speaking in English, Pia Palme holds her voice back, whispering, while playing her keyed bass recorder. The drone of the instrument and the rattles of its keys emphasize the uncanny feeling of being with this isolated island. Her voice sounds restricted, as if there is not enough space on the island to let it all out. The German text, in contrast, is spoken, neutral, without emphases. The voice of singer Anette Schön Müller on the other hand is also spoken, but projected. The voices seem to reverberate a moment on the island, a mind with many thoughts, entangled with the locality; a fragmented identity performed by different voicings. Through these elements, the piece evokes the perception of being with/on the island with those thoughts and feelings.

Outro

In this paper I tried to merge ideas of listening, autoethnography, and new materialism. I argue that intentionally listening for entanglements allows us to learn. By adopting a new materialist approach, the subject is not dissolved; rather, we are able to acknowledge our connectedness to the world and challenge conventional listening practices. We set waves in motion and hereby are able to effect transformation within and without.

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